

Dynamic Water Quality Sensor Placement in Water Distribution System Using an Evolutionary Algorithm

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Keywords: Water Quality, placement, optimization, metaheuristic algorithm, hydraulic and water quality model

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Introduction

The optimal placement of water quality sensors for detecting contamination events and determining their source is an active research topic [1]. This is mainly because of the costs associated with the type and number of sensors required, which implies that the few sensors that can be placed need to be at optimal locations. The deployment and maintenance of sensors, which require significant financial investments, also need to be accounted for in this context [2]. Over the past two decades, a large number of studies that focus on the optimal placement of water quality sensors for contamination events detection and source identification in Water Distribution System (WDS) have been presented in the literature [3]. As the sensor placement optimization problem is NP-hard (i.e. with exponential computational complexity), many different methods have been proposed to solve it, including Integer Programming (IP) and Evolutionary Algorithms (EAs) [4]. This paper proposes an EA-based placement method for dynamic water quality sensors, which adapts the sensor locations based on the number of suspected contamination sources. The proposed method aims at quickly and reliably detecting the occurrence of contamination events while minimising the number of sensors required.

Methodology

Figure 1a illustrates the proposed sensor placement method which consists of two steps. During the first step multiple contamination scenarios are generated randomly and the EPANET software is used to capture how the various contamination events affect the WDS. The EPANET results are stored in the impact matrix which will be used by the sensor placement optimisation solver. Here, the Contaminated Water Consumed Volume (CWCV) is considered to populate the impact matrix. During the second step the sensor placement optimisation solver which uses an EA is run to find the optimal sensor placements from the set of the potential solutions. An EA is a generic population-based metaheuristic optimization algorithm. The general scheme of an EA is shown in the Figure 1b. The novel aspect of the work described in this paper is that the number of contamination sources considered during the first step can vary, thereby simulating scenarios where contamination occurs at one or two (or multiple – but not considered in this study) sources, and optimal sensor placements tailored to each of these scenarios are sought. In this context, if dynamic sensors (i.e. that can move along the pipes are assumed to be available) the framework described in this paper aims at providing the optimal sensor locations for efficiently detecting events when different numbers of contamination sources are suspected.

Figure 1: Proposed placement method (a) and general scheme of an EA (b)

Results and Discussion

The sensor placement method proposed in this study has been tested on the Battle of the Water Sensor Network (BWSN) case-study network [5]. The BWSN includes one reservoir, two pumps, eight valves, one hundred twenty-six junctions,

and one hundred sixty-eight pipes. Each contamination event considered in this study has concentration of 10 mg/L and an injection time of 2 hours (between start and stop time). The source of the contamination event could be single or multiple (i.e. 2 locations).

To show an example of the results obtained, the following scenario is considered here. Firstly, contamination started to spread in the network from TANK-131 (see Figure 2b) - at time zero of the 50 hours EPANET simulation. At this point a single source of contamination is suspected and the optimally placed sensors located in junctions 10, 17, 23 and 32 (see Figure 2b) enable detecting that contamination event. The effectiveness of that sensor placement can be inferred by looking at the contamination regions in the WDS after 16 hours of simulations shown Figure 2a. This map shows five different colours in which blue colour represents a region with no contamination while red colour represents regions with high contaminations. After that, a second source of the contamination is suspected (simulated as a contamination event that started to spread in the network from RESERVOIR-129). Therefore, the sensors should move to the optimal locations in junctions 10, 31, 110 and 117 (see Figure 3b) to more effectively detect the 2-source contamination event. Similarly to what shown in Figure 2a, Figure 3a demonstrates the effectiveness of that sensor placement by showing the contamination regions after 30 hours of simulations.

Figure 2. Contamination spread after 16 hours (a) and optimal sensor placement for one contamination source (b)

Figure 3. Contamination spread after 30 hours (a) and optimal sensor placement for two contamination sources (b)

Conclusions

In this paper, a dynamic water quality sensor placement method that uses an EA is proposed. The proposed method consists of two steps. During the first step multiple contamination scenarios are generated randomly and the EPANET software is used to capture how the various contamination events affect the WDS. During the second step the sensor placement optimisation solver which uses an EA is run to find the optimal sensor placements. The novelty of this method is that it assumes the possibility of adapting the sensor locations based on the number of suspected contamination sources. The results obtained on the BWSN case-study demonstrate the capabilities of the proposed method.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. S. Perelman, W. Abbas, X. Koutsoukos, and S. Amin, "Sensor placement for fault location identification in water networks: A minimum test cover approach," *Automatica*, vol. 72, pp. 166-176, 2016.
- [2] D. Zeng, L. Gu, L. Lian, S. Guo, H. Yao, and J. Hu, "On cost-efficient sensor placement for contaminant detection in water distribution systems," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 12, pp. 2177-2185, 2016.
- [3] S. Rathi and R. Gupta, "Optimal sensor locations for contamination detection in pressure-deficient water distribution networks using genetic algorithm," *Urban Water Journal*, vol. 14, pp. 160-172, 2017.
- [4] G. He, T. Zhang, F. Zheng, and Q. Zhang, "An efficient multi-objective optimization method for water quality sensor placement within water distribution systems considering contamination probability variations," *Water research*, vol. 143, pp. 165-175, 2018.
- [5] A. Ostfeld, J. G. Uber, E. Salomons, J. W. Berry, W. E. Hart, C. A. Phillips, *et al.*, "The battle of the water sensor networks (BWSN): A design challenge for engineers and algorithms," *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, vol. 134, pp. 556-568, 2008.